

APPLICATION OF MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH.

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Abstract: One of the most crucial components of tolerance in a personality culture is language learning. Since language is a tool for communication, it can be learned nearly anywhere—at home, in the community, or in a formal setting. Additionally, theory-based instruction is given on language phenomena. Language proficiency, especially multilingualism, is extremely important in today's world of active international interactions. In our country, most pupils and foreign students learn three languages. Special names are used to identify these languages. Native language, second language, and foreign language are these. The first language that functions independently in the development of thinking is the native tongue. The second language is treated as the language of its fraternity, or neighbors, which are made up of people from various nationalities when it is spoken. In this article, opinions and feedback on the use of modern methods in teaching English are kept.

Keywords: English, methodology, modern, technology, teaching, speech, didactic education, interactive education.

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There are distinct concepts in each science. The educational system, the educational method, the educational principle, the educational methods, and the methodological approach are some of the key ideas incorporated into the methodology of teaching a foreign language. When a method of teaching a foreign language is referred to as a complex of actions involving both a teacher and a student, it means that it aims to meet the practical, all-encompassing, educational, and developmental objectives of doing so. The terms "sum of educational techniques" and "direction of Education" are used to refer to different aspects of education. The second meaning can be found in works on the history of teaching methodology, whereas the first is employed in educational theory in the sense of process techniques. For instance, teaching a foreign language is referred to as a translation method, conscious-comparative approach, traditional way, intensive method, etc.

The phenomena of nature and society develop in interconnected and continuous communication. Since the sciences are the unics of objective reality, none of them exists separated from the others. The phenomenon and the subject at the same time can be a source of research in several disciplines, for example, the social phenomenon "language" from its point of view is studied by linguistics, educational science. The term "methodology of a foreign language" evokes in the mind of a person the so-called associative "connection": first of all, the totality of

methods and approaches aimed at teaching a language is understood or scientific knowledge about teaching methods, and finally, independent pedagogical science comes to mind. The methodology of teaching a foreign language has developed in harmony with didactics, interconnected. It is undoubtedly known to all of us that the teaching theories of all academic disciplines are based on didactics, from which they receive scientific feed. Foreign Language Teaching is also based on didactics.

Linguodidactics, general theory of didactics in education, methodology as the science of instruction Linguometodics is regarded as the science of teaching a particular language, according to the General Theory of Language Teaching. The word "method" refers to the process through which a teacher-educator and student work to acquire knowledge, credentials, skills, the development of students' worldviews, and the provision of opportunities for cognition. There are numerous ways to define this idea. The implementation of techniques in teaching foreign languages began in distant times, while the principles are relatively newer methodological terms. The statement of grammatical knowledge was accepted as the main goal of the teaching. The basic principles of this method are as follows:

1. Language learning is based on written speech.
2. Grammar was taken as the subject of study, the lexicon was also selected subject to it. Performing grammatical exercises is the main working method.
3. Before, the grammatical rule was memorized, and then it was recommended to compose sentences based on the rules.
4. The grammatical form and the meaning of words are revealed literally in the translation tool.
5. By literal translation and dry memorization, the language material is assimilated.
6. It is limited to memorizing words in isolation, out of context.

This approach has been used in a number of historical forms. They fall into two categories: natural methods and mountain ways. The conditions of mastering the native language should be comparable to those of learning a foreign language in a natural way. The practical goal develops the notion that the method's primary objective is to provide students with the opportunity to learn to read and write through speaking a foreign language. The establishment of a language environment is the most significant of the principles that make up the natural approach. Various approaches have appeared in the chapter on the practical application of the proposed methodological principles. This can be clearly felt in the creative activity of the manifestations of the method.

Learning a second language is a multidimensional process that involves significant psychological growth for the learner. Particularly prevalent is the

technique of contrasting a foreign language with one's mother tongue. Different training methods and technology are applied in this process. Modern pedagogical technology make it possible to teach a foreign language effectively by comparing it to one's home tongue. Understanding a foreign language's technique is necessary for teaching it. The use of methodology and techniques is crucial when learning a foreign language. When organizing a lesson, there are various methods of methodological science. Methods widely used in the methodology of teaching a foreign language are: the method of communicative didactics, the method of organizing intercultural communication and the method of organizing the exercise. All three methods are closely related and complement each other. Since the science of methodology is associated with the science of didactics, during the study of a foreign language, it is based on communicativeness, and the method of communicative didactics occurs.

The pedagogical method for fostering cross-cultural communication is also developed with the application of communicative didactics. Learning a foreign language also involves mastering that nation's culture. The "technique of structuring an activity" is crucial for acquiring the knowledge required in foreign language teaching. The best way to assimilate all knowledge is through exercise. The activity is beneficial for learning a foreign language as well as for mastering all subject-matter knowledge. The effective organization of the lesson, the role of pedagogical activity and modern pedagogical technologies in it are incomparable. It is important to organize the process of learning a foreign language with an approach to communicativeness, to bring the next stage to the level of intercultural communication, to achieve such results, to focus on yes, the last step, "exercise technology". For the consequent Organization of the process of teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to master the knowledge of modern pedagogical information and communication technologies.

Techniques that are active or interactive encourage student autonomy and cognitive activity. In order to create a welcoming learning atmosphere where all students actively engage one another, interactive methods are used. The modeling of real-world scenarios, the employment of role-playing games, the general information solution based on the analysis of tasks and situations, and the introduction of information flows into the mind that prompt its active participation are all part of the organization of interactive education. An integral part of interactive approaches are interactive exercises and tasks performed by students. The main differences in interactive exercises and routine work, they are aimed not only at combining the material studied, but also at learning something new. Modern pedagogy is rich in many interactive approaches, among which are the following:

1. tasks of creativity
2. work in small groups
3. educational games (role playing, imitation, Business games and educational games)
4. use of public resources (inviting specialists, excursions)
5. social projects (social projects, contests, radio and newspapers, films, shows, exhibitions, performances, songs and fairy tales)
6. learning and strengthening new materials (interactive lecture, visual aids, work with video and audio materials, "student as a teacher", "everyone teaches everyone".
7. discussion of complex and controversial questions and problems.

The interactive learning approach allows for direct student-to-student communication inside the learning setting, which also acts as a learning resource. Interaction implies the preparation of students and teachers while structuring their training when discussing pedagogical strategies. Instead of acting as a listener or a spectator, the reader actively engages in the lesson. Not just kids from the school Bali Lyceum, College, or higher education become full participants with such an organizational structure of the educational process. The task of the teacher is, in principle, to stimulate independent activities, to find ways to achieve their goals. One of the main tasks is to improve the pedagogical skills of the teacher by mastering modern teaching and educational technologies. With the application of any new technologies, new pedagogical ideas of the teacher begin: the clarity of the systematic, methodological language, the emergence of clear tactics in the educational methodology.

In conclusion, The student's own particular interests are the most crucial responsibility of the educational process. Knowing which technology to incorporate into the teaching process will help you get the desired results. As you can see, regardless of how flawless a certain educational technology is used, it does not produce the best conditions for identifying and developing students' qualifications. The technology of pedagogical education - together with a favorable environment for students and teachers for the design, organization and conduct of the educational process, is told a well-thought-out model of educational and pedagogical activity. Pedagogical technology involves the implementation of a completely controlled idea of the educational process.

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